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Leading with Ego: How Narcissistic Leadership Fuels Counterproductive Behaviors through Organizational Cynicism in Public Sector Banks of Pakistan

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Abstract

“Leadership is not about being in charge. It is about taking care of those in your charge.” —Simon Sinek. In this rapidly evolving business world, staying ahead is not only a matter of strategies it needs augmentation of leadership that ensures embracing the change rather than to resist. In developing countries, public sector organizations are facing chronic problem of true leadership. This study aimed to highlight the indispensable role of leadership by examining how narcissistic leadership nurture organizational cynicism and its three dimensions —cognitive, emotional, and behavioral—and its impact on counterproductive work behaviors within the banking sector. Beneath the umbrella of Social Exchange Theory and Leader—Member Exchange Theory, data of 419 employees from the banking industry in Pakistan were collected and analyzed using Partial Least Square- Structure Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). This study employed standardized scales to measure various constructs of study which were assessed through measurement model. Structural model findings reflected that that narcissistic leadership strongly predicts all dimensions of cynicism, but only behavioral cynicism dimension mediates the relationship between narcissistic leadership and counterproductive behavior. The study accentuates how narcissistic leadership erodes sentiments and escalates deviances which leads to failure of organizations. These findings reinforce the notion that even if one dimension of cynicism is driving negative behaviors, this type of leadership can ruin the employee well-being and organizational health. This study has also highlighted various theoretical, practical and social implications which can set the guidelines for practitioners.

Keywords: Narcissistic Leadership, Social Exchange Theory, Pakistani Banking Sector, Organizational Cynicism, Counterproductive Behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Today is the time of dynamic, rapidly changing and fast-paced environment wherein the organizations are constantly navigating a landscape shaped by intense competition, globalization, technological innovation, and shifting market demands (Li, 2024) and staying ahead requires more than just a solid strategy—it demands effective leadership (Attah et al., 2023). Without capable leadership, even the most carefully planned strategies are likely to fall short (Behie et al., 2023). Whether you look at the inspiring success of leaders like Nelson Mandela and Dr. Muhammad Yunus of Grameen Bank or the failures of the leaders like Fred Goodwin of Royal Bank of Scotland or other figures whose ego and poor judgement led organizations to collapse, one thing gets clear—it’s the leadership traits that consistently shape the outcome, for better or worse. It is the leadership that drives vision, aligns people with organizational goals, and ensures that change is embraced rather than resisted (Håland, 2024; Mwamba, 2023).

Leadership is not merely a position of authority but a role that involves influencing, motivating, and empowering individuals toward

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achieving shared goals by shaping organizational culture, better communication, and by building trust among employees (Jerab & Mabrouk, 2023) through clarity, emotional intelligence, and strong decision-making abilities (Yuldasheva, 2024). Good leadership brings numerous advantages that significantly enhance an organization's performance by fostering a positive work environment by encouraging collaboration and innovation (Goenaga, 2024; Zhang, 2024).

When people feel heard and valued through involved decision making, they try harder which directly impacts the organization's success (Kwarteng et al., 2024) and strengthen morale and ownership among employees, leading to a stronger sense of community (Edward Godbless, 2021). However, not all leaders have a positive influence i.e. toxic leadership and abusive leadership attributes styles can have destructive impact on both individuals and whole organization (Octavian, 2023). Among these, narcissistic leadership (NL) who is often self-centered, overly concerned with their image, and dismissive of others' contributions are particularly harmful (Bernerth, 2022; Bernerth et al., 2022). They crave admiration, dominate decision-making, and are quick to take credit for successes while deflecting blame for failures (Webster, 2021). This type of leadership lacks empathy and discourages open dialogue, leading to a work environment filled with tension, fear, and discontent (Masubelele, 2024).

NL can harm employee well-being by making subordinates feel devalued, overlooked, and emotionally exhausted (Khan et al., 2022) which undermines psychological safety, leading to increased stress, burnout, and in many cases, high employee turnover (Li & Peng, 2022). Over time, not only it affects individual as well as collective effectiveness of teams and overall organizational climate becomes one of distrust, resistance, and disengagement (Peng et al., 2023) but also causing Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs) and Organizational Cynicism (OC) (Mousa et al., 2021). When employees experience consistent mistreatment or manipulation from their leaders, they may resort to behavior that harms organization through reduced effort, absenteeism, or subtle acts of defiance (Octavian, 2023). CWBs often stem from frustration, helplessness, or a desire to regain a sense of control and employees may develop cynical attitudes towards organization, doubting its values, leadership, and integrity (M. A. O. Ahmed et al., 2024) and erodes loyalty and suppresses motivation, ultimately impeding growth and long-term success (Saban, 2024).

In true essence, quality of leadership plays major part in shaping the future (Najihah, 2024) and while strong, empathetic, and inclusive leadership can inspire excellence and innovation, NL and abusive leadership styles can lead to dysfunction and decline (Khorram-Manesh et al., 2024). Recognizing the profound impact of leadership on both people and performance is essential for building a sustainable, high-performing organization (Kasim, 2021).

Previous studies have found a direct link between NL and negative outcomes like distress, burnout, emotional exhaustion and CWBs (Badar et al., 2023; Faeq, 2025; Khan et al., 2022; Murad et al., 2021). Further, it has also been established that OC contributes

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enormously to the rise of CWBs (Griep et al., 2023; Naseer et al., 2021; Ugwu et al., 2023). However, despite these recognized relations, an important gap remains unchecked in the literature which is the mediating role of OC in the relationship of NL and CWBs. Studies have explored dyadic links like NL and OC or OC and CWBs but very rare if any have explored empirically and full mediation model keeping these three constructs with in a single framework. Unearthing this mechanism is very crucial as how the NL indirectly promotes the CWBs by nurturing cynical organizational climate i.e. OC. This study aims to cover this theoretical and empirical gap by investigating whether OC acts as a mediator in the relationship of NL and the CWBs.

HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

This section includes the previous studies and work related to current study and explains the relationships of NL, CWB, and OC (OCC, OCE, & OCB) that forms the basis of conceptual model of this study.

Relationship between Narcissistic Leadership (NL) and Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs)

The idea of “narcissism” started from word “narcissus”, that infers three main features: “(1) inflated self-concept; (2) interpersonal exploitation; and (3) inordinate need for tribute from others” (Liao et al., 2019). It can better be explained by following “a highly inflated, excessively positive, and exaggerated view of oneself” (Neufeld & Johnson, 2016). The narcissists always exhibit illusions full of greatness, dominance and restless competition (Li et al., 2023). They always feel that they are higher and central being who focus on themselves (Li et al., 2024). The gravity of narcissistic behaviors in an organizational context can never be overlooked as a lot of leaders act narcissistically (Owens et al., 2015).

The personality traits of narcissism are depicted by four significant ways which are (Li et al., 2023): (1) Charisma: they always encompass crucial communication abilities, futuristic analysis abilities and a mesmerizing personality. (2) Egoistic motives: they keep their interests higher than the organizational goals and objectives. (3) Deceptive motives: they use employees for their personal gains. (4) Knowledge inhibition: they always love to be praised and even a sincere criticism can raise their hostility towards the concerned. Resultantly, although narcissists can be inspiring to their followers and subordinates yet they can be very destructive for the teams and organizations (Azazz et al., 2024).

Few previous research studies have enormously exhibited relationship between NL and CWBs (Gulbahar et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2024; Mghazli & Evans, 2021) and a meta-analytical study has acknowledged many important conclusions which were linked with NL leading to negative outcomes at workplace and most importantly (CWBs) (Lartey et al., 2024). Schyns and Schilling (2013), stated that the outcomes might appear in different ways like discomfort with work and leader, thinking to leave the organization, less or no commitment, least amount of mutual well-being, and most importantly the lowest level of employee productivity.

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The antagonistic impact of Dark Triangle on the workplace has potentially been the main agenda of research in organizational controversies (Nübold et al., 2017). Many reasons acknowledge that the NL stimulates negative employee behaviors, (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003; Burger et al., 2009; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005), and the exchange norms like tit for tat. In the supervision of NL, the employees often intend to work with less commitment and have a very negative intentions towards performance of their jobs to their full capacity (Tepper, 2000). Subordinating employees and team members exhibit certain downward adjustments in behaviors through huge participation in CWBs, which are the harmful initiatives that individuals start for the company and its members. Conclusively, NL and CWBs have a healthy relation which can really impact the organization. The correlation NL and CWBs has also been endorsed by the research studies undertaken by Tepper et al. (2009) and Brender-Ilan and Sheaffer (2019).

Aghaz et al. (2014) acknowledged narcissistic behaviors to be the most robust prophet of individual as well as organizational negative outcomes such as CWBs. Accordingly Braun (2017), revised the basic positive and negative results of NL. The conclusions of a multi-level analysis inferred that the NL always have a negative influence over the behaviors of subordinates in form of CWBs and negative citizenship behavior at the individual, group and organizational levels. Employees at all levels have presumed frustration, stress, or pain because of self-praise in all tasks and jobs which results in CWBs.

H1. Narcissistic Leadership (NL) impacts Counterproductive Work behaviors (CWBs) positively.

Relationship between Narcissistic Leadership (NL) and Organizational Cynicism (OC)

NL in the organizational domain has a very strong impact on the workplace environment (J. B. Carnevale et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2022). Many latest empirical evidence based researches have pointed out a strong link between NL and undesired negative outcomes from subordinates like no job engagement, employee silence, team spirit and limited or no creativity (J. Carnevale et al., 2018; Fehn & Schütz, 2021; Norouzinik et al., 2022). Moreover, Hooseini et al. (2023) reasoned that the acts and manners of NL harm their followers and subordinates emotionally and forbids them by replying to their criticism damagingly. NL is presumed to be self-benefiting rather than his subordinates and organization. Employees' work behaviors can be controlled through managing the leader impression tactics to balance leader-member exchange.

OC is explained and defined to be three dimensional responses—believes, attitudes (emotional reactions), and behaviors aimed at the organization (Dean Jr et al., 1998). Dean Jr et al. (1998) extensively explained and divided OC into categories. They stated that the employees' negative response in organizational direction comes through three dimensions which are the belief that organization is not honest, an emotional reaction that organization is patronizing, and a negative citizenship behavior towards the organization (Dean Jr et

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al., 1998). Andersson (1996) stated it as hatred, despair, frustration and suspicion headed for an individual, a team, a concept, or an organization (Andersson, 1996). The work of Atwater et al. (2000), modeled OC as weak connection with the organization, negative perception of the organization and a thrust to indulge in negative organizational behaviors. It states a scenario wherein it is assumed a deficient reciprocated responses of organization and ignorance of morals or standards like meritocracy, integrity, comprehensiveness only for personal gains (Atwater et al., 2000). It seems that OC appears as a reactive self–protection mechanism to deal with thoughts of dissatisfaction towards the deeds of organization and its leadership (Abraham, 2000; Reichers et al., 1997).

OCC transpires when employees observe their efforts are unappreciated and start questioning their leaders' impartiality, righteousness, and authenticity. These perceptions and feelings navigate employees to develop negative expectations about the leadership's objectives and actions. (Dean et al., 1998; Kim et al., 2009). OCE is mostly based on the employees' emotional reactions manipulated by their personal beliefs and experiences. For instance, when it is observed that the leaders lack integrity, cynical employees foster negative emotional states including disdain and anger towards their leaders. They might also encounter anxiety, disgust, irritation, provocation, and even humiliation (Brandes, 1997; Chiaburu et al., 2013; Dean et al., 1998; Kim et al., 2009). OCB is expressed through negative and disparaging employee attitudes (Brandes, 1997). As the ancient cynics in organizations articulated their cynicism by way of adopting extreme criticism of their leaders (Dean et al., 1998). Additionally, sarcastic humor, gloomy predictions about the company, and nonverbal behaviors like hatred and disapproval are other reactions linked to OCB (Brandes, 1997; Dean et al., 1998).

Past research studies have endorsed that NL can be of an inconsistent influence on workplace behaviors of employees (Grijalva & Newman, 2015). Negative leadership style is known to be the most crucial cause of negative workplace behaviors like less productivity issues, higher intentions to quit, low motivation, OC, and higher job dissatisfaction (Maheshwari, 2022). The best employees who have already been achieving the organizational goals would not be able to achieve the organizational goals if their negative attitudes like cynicism has been triggered or stimulated (Giliç & İnandi, 2021). Perceptions of upper level of OC inversely influences productivity, development, self-confidence, and collaborative decision making.

H2. Narcissistic Leadership (NL) has an impact on Organizational Cynicism (OC) in public banks of Pakistan.

H2 (a). Narcissistic Leadership (NL) has an impact on Cognitive Cynicism (OCC) in public banks of Pakistan.

H2 (b). Narcissistic Leadership (NL) has an impact on Emotional Cynicism (OCE) in public banks of Pakistan.

H2 (c). Narcissistic Leadership (NL) has an impact on Behavioral Cynicism (OCB) in public banks of Pakistan.

Organizational Cynicism (OC) and Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs)

OC is the mental state that has been considered with the irritated feelings, emotional disappointments, and despair about the

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organization, which ultimately causes negative results like a huge decrease in employee productivity, employee performance, and decreased employee commitment (Acaray & Yildirim, 2017). OCC or negative mindset usually triggers undesired links with employee performance, and OCE increases self-serving behaviors, higher individual and interpersonal retaliations, higher intentions to quit, and increased absenteeism (Bang & Reio Jr, 2017). Furthermore, with the OCB employees indulge in aggressive and critical interchanges damage the organizational image and destructively impact the organizational environment which also reflects the lowest level of employee commitment towards the organization (Agina et al., 2023; Serrano Archimi et al., 2018). OC has now been generally accepted as a rapidly emerging issue in the workplace settings which require to be tackled on basis of war-footings (Shahzad & Mahmood, 2012).

Depending on the relation with leaders, OC stops the employees from using the necessary resources to do their jobs efficiently and effectively and resultantly this sets a tone for increase in the stress and psychological pressure which leads the OC to be more skeptical towards the organization (Cheng, 2024). According to Rayan et al. (2018) two dimensions of OC which has impact on CWBs are OCE and OCB this can be because of many workplace settings and leadership is one of those. Cultivating a harmonious organization culture among employees is crucial for the organizations because when Organizations fail to cultivate a culture through which employee needs, expectations, honesty, meritocracy and fairness is not achieved, this results in employee dissatisfaction which leads to lowest employee commitment towards the organization (Brandes et al., 1999). These negative feelings of employees turn into harmful behaviors of employees at workplace because of the pressures created by the organizational practices and NL approach (Nemteanu & Dabija, 2021; Yiwen & Hahn, 2021) and CWBs are the most prominent.

Sabir et al. (2024), stated that CWBs take place when the organizational employees intentionally damage the company, its members or other employees, the organizational goals and objectives and even the interests of external stakeholders. These actions and intentions which are intentional in nature to damage, break rules, destroy organizational beliefs, and being a danger to organization and its members wellbeing and safety are considered as CWBs. Gervasi et al. (2022) implied that CWBs are happenings that harm organizations and its employees and the overall synergy at workplace. Ultimately, CWBs cause waste and inefficiency in organizational useful resources which further causes a drop in work quality (Colquitt, 2001). Resultantly with time, it has a negative influence on coworkers and whole organization and ultimately organizations lose its potential to fulfill the organizational responsibilities effectively (Gervasi et al., 2022).

These negative outcomes can be a result of wasteful use of time and resources, bad use of information, misconduct, misuse of office supplies, exploitation of organizational resources, absentees and careless job performance (Colquitt, 2001). On the other hand the employees indulging in these behavioral tendencies might lose their reputation at work and penalized when their negative behaviors are

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unearthed (Aisha et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2022). M. A. O. Ahmed et al. (2024), narrated CWBs are intentional actions of individuals to destroy and harm the overall safety and well-being of an organization. By this, both the organizations and their employees suffer immensely when employees perform in destructive manner on the workplace (Kim & Yoon, 2017). These CWBs arise and occur due to the complex contact between employee and their surroundings in the workplace especially when the employee has a belief of unfavorable outcomes (Miao & Zhou, 2020).

Research studies done by Wilkerson et al. (2008) and Yıldız and Şaylıkay (2014), state that OC is explained as a negative attitude of employees directed towards the organizations and these prolonged negative feelings and attitudes in isolation turn into worst negative behaviors like questioning and criticizing organizational policies, philosophy, and culture. There is a direct relationship between OC and CWBs as described by Evans et al. (2010). Research studies of Tong et al. (2020) endorsed that OC anticipates the CWBs. Conclusively, it is evident that there is a very strong and direct correlation between the OC and CWBs which was also stated by Dar et al. (2020).

H3. The Organizational Cynicism (OC) has an impact on Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

H3 (a). The Cognitive Organizational Cynicism (OCC) has an impact on Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

H3 (b). The Emotional Organizational Cynicism (OCE) has an impact on Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

H3 (c). The Behavioral Organizational Cynicism (OCB) has an impact on Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

The mediating role of Organizational Cynicism (OC) between Narcissistic Leadership (NL) and Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

Graen and Uhl-Bien (1995) in their research work infer that leader–member exchange hypothesis (LMX) speculates that leaders and supervisors behave differently with their different subordinates. This leader-member exchange (LMX) relation decides the strength of this individual level workplace connection between an employee and his leader whether it is based on shared traits of working abilities, trust, fairness and shared goals (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995; Pan et al., 2020). These relationships are based on the series of different interactions occurring at workplace settings. Leaders and superiors deal with their subordinates and employees differently and mainly depending on the interactions and nature of relationship taking place during the workplace settings (M. A. O. Ahmed et al., 2024; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

Leader-member exchange (LMX) hypothesis explains the prospects and dynamics of such work conduct and it states that leaders may express biased approach towards certain employee or group of employees while discouraging and undermining other member or group of members (Mostafa et al., 2021). Resultantly, it nurtures an environment of uneasiness and OC (OCC, OCE, & OCB) causing a huge decline in the ability of working together as teams and generation of creative new ideas (Kirrane et al., 2019). This explains that how an

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unbalanced approach to leader–member exchange (LMX) anticipates the overall feeling of widespread OC among employees. Leadership may be a cause of two dimensions of OC i.e. OCE and OCB to arise CWBs from the employees in workplace settings (Rayan et al., 2018). In organization at workplace, the employees may experience disappointment and detachment if they feel any kind of unjust and unfair conduct and it will result in reduced level of effort, low level of trust in leadership, and ever frustration and this conclusively causes CWBs (M. A. O. Ahmed et al., 2024; Seo et al., 2024).

H4: Organizational Cynicism (OC) mediates the relationship between Narcissistic Leadership (NL) and Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

H4 (a): Cognitive Organizational Cynicism (OCC) mediates the relationship between Narcissistic Leadership (NL) and Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

H4 (b): Emotional Organizational Cynicism (OCE) mediates the relationship between Narcissistic Leadership (NL) and Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

H4 (c): Behavioral Organizational Cynicism (OCB) mediates the relationship between Narcissistic Leadership (NL) and Counterproductive Work Behaviors (CWBs).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is sheltered by two contemporary theories which are Social Exchange Theory (SET) and Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory to elaborate the relationship dynamics that how NL the employees' attitudes and behaviors. Social Exchange Theory (SET), as theorized by Blau (1964), emphasizes that workplace interactions are grounded in the principle of tit for tat, where individuals maintain relationships based on the balance of inputs and outcomes. When leaders act fairly and respectfully, employees tend to respond with loyalty and positive behaviors. On the contrary, when employees notice an imbalance—such as being ill-treated, exploited, or undervalued—they may engage in negative reciprocity in the form of disengagement, distrust, or retaliatory actions (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005).

Within this framework, NL—characterized by superiority, self-centeredness, entitlement, and a lack of empathy (Rosenthal & Pittinsky, 2006)—can severely damage the leader–member exchange relationship. NL often prioritize self-interest over employee well-being, ignore input from subordinates, and violate relational expectations (Braun, 2016). Such behavior signals to employees that the organization does not value or respect them, leading to a breakdown of trust and OC—a deep-seated attitude marked by touch of frustration, skepticism, and disappointment towards the organization (Dean Jr et al., 1998). OC from the SET lens, becomes a psychological reaction to unmet expectations and perceived social injustice. Furthermore, SET also explains the progression from OC to

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CWBs. Employees who grow cynical may engage in CWBs—such as intentional inefficiency, tardiness, withdrawal, or interpersonal deviance—as a retaliatory mechanism to balance the social exchange relationship (Skarlicki & Folger, 1997). In this sense, CWBs are not random acts of misconduct, but calculated responses to perceived betrayal by the organization and its leadership.

To further illuminate the direct relationship between NL and CWBs, the study incorporates Leader–Member Exchange (LMX) theory. LMX theory postulates that leaders formulate inconsistent relationships with subordinates—some of high quality (characterized by trust and mutual support) and others of low quality (defined by limited communication and formal role-based interaction) (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995). NL, due to the self-centered nature and need for admiration, often form superficial or manipulative relationships, showing favoritism toward a select few while alienating others (Nevicka et al., 2011). Subordinates who find themselves in low-quality LMX relationships are more prone to experience emotional detachment, job dissatisfaction, and reduced commitment, which in turn increases their likelihood of engaging in CWBs (Erdogan & Enders, 2007).

In summary, SET explains the indirect pathway in which NL erodes trust, fuels OC, and leads to CWBs through negative reciprocity. LMX theory complements this by explaining the direct relationship—how NL fail to establish strong, equitable exchanges with employees, fostering resentment and deviant workplace behaviors. The current study engages SET as it provides theoretical foundation for reciprocal exchanges and LMX is employed to form theoretical foundation to understand leadership processes and quality of leader member exchanges.

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Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

The combination of these theories offers a well-rounded and holistic understanding of both the mediated and direct effects of NL on CWBs through comprehensive explanation of how reciprocal exchanges incur within leader-member exchanges.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study was quantitative in nature and collected empirical data through cross-sectional research design. The main objective of this study was to test the mediation effect of OC between the relationship of NL and CWBs, therefore, quantitative approach was more aligned.

Target Population and Sampling

This study focused on the public sector banking industry of Pakistan. The individuals who were working in public sector banks at the time of our study and have at least 3 years of banking experience would make the population of study. Further, these individuals must have experience of direct supervision of organizational processes. From this population, sample was selected through convenience sampling.

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Further, to mitigate the researcher potential bias during data collection from a single district or province, the data was collected from linkedIn through google forms and respondents were not from a single city or province.

Generalization of study findings are mainly dependent of representative sample size. Out of many approaches to determine appropriate sample size, two widely used approaches have been considered here (1) estimation of sample size through appropriate statistical formula (2) Minimum sample size required for statistical analysis in the study. In this study we considered both the mentioned approaches. Firstly, we used the formula proposed by Yamane (1973) as the size of population was known. Many researchers have used this formula previously (Clement, 2024; Daniel & Eze, 2016; Israel, 1992; Musyoki et al., 2024) that enhanced the validity, reliability, and acceptability of this formula. The formula is

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where n is sample size, N is total population and e is the margin of error. The total population of this study after application of inclusion criteria was 25071 and the margin of error equivalent to 0.05 in this study as was recommended by the previous researchers (Clement, 2024; Daniel & Eze, 2016; Israel, 1992; Musyoki et al., 2024). Here the sample size is

$$n = \frac{25071}{1 + 25071(0.5)^2}$$

$$n = 394$$

The formula suggested the selection of 394 employees as a representative sample size.

As per the second approach, sample size should be aligned with the main statistical technique which was planned in this study; Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). As per guidelines, minimum sample size of 200 is considered acceptable for SEM model stability and accuracy (Kline, 2023; Sarstedt et al., 2021). After consideration of both the approaches to calculate the sample size, the researchers considered sample size of 394 as appropriate to fulfill criteria of both the approaches to enhance the generalizability of this study. Before, the execution of main study, pilot survey was also executed on a small sample of 50 respondents and 30 questionnaires were returned with a response rate of 60%. Considering this response rate sample size was inflated to 650 to get at least a sample of 394. A total of 650 respondents were contacted and out of those we received 419 completed responses and as the questionnaire was used through google forms, there were no incomplete forms. The total response rate was 64.46% which is considerably satisfactory in this nature of study (M. A. O. Ahmed et al., 2024). This sample is higher than the estimated, however, completely filled questionnaire can be used in the study.

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Data Collection Methods

Data was collected through a well-structured and online survey. Google form was shared in the form of a link via email and through professional social media platforms (i.e. LinkedIn and WhatsApp groups). The online format was to ensure a wider geographic reach and convenience for respondents while maintaining anonymity. Before the collection of data, the ethical permission was taken from the relevant respondents and were thoroughly informed about main objective and purpose of this study, and it was ensured that their participation was on voluntary basis. Prior consent was also obtained and it was assured to them that their information would be used only for research purpose and kept confidential.

Research Instruments

This study used three constructs which have been measured through standardized and previously validated scales. The five-points Likert scale was used to measure each item in questionnaire which ranged from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). In this study, the independent variable i.e. NL was measured using 10 items and out of those 4 items were adopted from (Hendin & Cheek, 1997) and 06 items were taken from the scale of (Hochwarter & Thompson, 2012) and same were also used by previous researchers (Aboramadan et al., 2020; Gaughran, 2023; Gubler et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022). The dependent variable i.e. CWBs was measured through 7 items and those were taken from (Kelloway et al., 2002) which were also used by various researchers (M. A. O. Ahmed et al., 2024; Carpenter et al., 2021; Choi et al., 2024). The mediating variable i.e. three dimensions of OC i.e. OCC, OCE, and OCB were measured through 04 items for each and were adopted from (Durrah et al., 2019) and were used by previous researchers (A. K. Ahmed et al., 2024; Atalay et al., 2022; Durrah et al., 2023; KUCHARSKI, 2025; Mirzaei & Aghighi, 2024). The use of same items by other similar researches justifies the validity and reliability of the chosen instruments. A pilot study was conducted with a small subset (30 potential participants) to ensure clarity and internal consistency of the items. However, these 30 questionnaires and participants were removed from further processing to avoid any further bias.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data was analyzed through Smartpls 4.0 for developing SEM model and mediation analysis. Initially, measurement and structural models were developed. In the measurement model, reliability and validity of constructs were assessed by following standard protocols explained in the literature. Composite reliability (CR), Cronbach's Alpha, factor loadings have been used for construct validity and reliability. Later, discriminant validity was also assessed through HTMT ratio and cross loadings. After confirmation of measurement model, direct and indirect relationship, and most importantly the mediating role of OC, in relationship of NL and CWBs were estimated. The significance of these paths have also been tested at 5% level of significance.

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Assessment of Common Method Bias (CMB)

As per guiding principle of Podsakoff et al. (2012), common method bias should be tested before developing SEM models. Therefore, considering the test proposed by Kock (2015), variance inflation factor (VIF) was also estimated for all latent construct by regressing two constructs on other common construct. This process repeated by taking three types of OC, CWB and NL as dependent construct sequentially. Results have shown that there is no issue of CMB as VIF values in regression models were less than 3.3 which showed no contamination of CMB in the constructs.

RESULTS

SmartPLS has been very accredited tool in most of the social sciences studies and being used worldwide with a significant authenticity (Hair et al., 2019; Nazish et al., 2023). It offers a complete protocol of assessing and reporting of validity, reliability of constructs and ultimately estimation of path coefficients. Initially, basic demographic analysis has been presented in Table 1. In this study all the respondents were from public sector banks with experience more than 03 years. These two features belong to inclusion criteria of study. Threshold value of minimum experience is essential to understand the culture and organizational philosophy. In current study, 78% of the respondents were young and early career; between the age range of 26-40. Almost 2/3rd (64%) of respondents were male and reflected that public sector banks are having male dominating culture. All the respondents had acceptable experience from 3 to 20+ years of experience. The data also showed that more than 70% respondents were having Masters/M.Phil/MS/PhD degrees which shows that the respondents were equipped with good academic understanding.

Table 2 contains the information of measurement model for types of OC, CWBs and NL. All five constructs demonstrated acceptable levels of validity and reliability as per CR and AVE values. These findings indicate the reasonable measurement quality in the constructs and their connections.

Table 1: *Demographic Characteristics of Public Sector Banks Employees*

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (Years)		
26-40	327	78%
41-56	92	22%
Gender		
Male	268	64%
Females	151	36%

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Education

Bachelors	122	29%
Masters	205	49%
M.Phil/MS	88	21%
PhD	4	1%

Experience(Years)

3-10	256	61%
11-20	131	31%
Above 20	32	8%

Assessment of Measurement Model: Reliability and Validity of Constructs

The measurement model has been reported in Table 2 and showed that all the factor loadings were greater than 0.70. Initial measurement model was consisted of 29 items (10 items for NL, 4 items for each type of OC; OCC, OCE and OCB and 7 items for CWB). However, two items CWB2 and OCB1 were removed from the model because of low factor loadings; 0.57 and 0.54, respectively. The model was re-run after deletion of these two items and yielded good measurement model. The finalized model also confirmed the presence of composite reliability (CR) in the constructs; greater than 0.70. According to literature, the factor loadings more than 0.708 and CR values greater than 0.70 confirm the validity and internal consistency (Hair et al., 2019). Internal consistency was also confirmed through conservative approach; Cronbach Alpha. Table 2 indicates that all five constructs exhibit high reliability: NL ($\alpha = 0.946$), OCC ($\alpha = 0.881$), OCB ($\alpha = 0.813$), OCE ($\alpha = 0.895$) and CWB ($\alpha = 0.933$) as per guidelines in the literature (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 2: Assessment of Measurement Model

Construct	Items	Factor Loading	AVE	CR	α
NL	NL1	0.821	0.668	0.952	0.946
	NL2	0.849			
	NL3	0.774			
	NL4	0.869			
	NL5	0.741			
	NL6	0.816			
	NL7	0.865			

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	NL8	0.755			
	NL9	0.847			
	NL10	0.823			
OCC	OCC1	0.903	0.737	0.918	0.881
	OCC2	0.851			
	OCC3	0.864			
	OCC4	0.814			
OCE	OCE1	0.798	0.742	0.920	0.895
	OCE2	0.882			
	OCE3	0.874			
	OCE4	0.888			
OCB	OCB2	0.795	0.730	0.890	0.813
	OCB3	0.871			
	OCB4	0.894			
CWB	CWB1	0.809	0.749	0.947	0.933
	CWB3	0.841			
	CWB4	0.921			
	CWB5	0.819			
	CWB6	0.888			
	CWB7	0.908			

Table 3 and 4 contain information of two measures of discriminant validity; HTMT ratio and Fornell and Larcker Criterion. The resulting values of HTMT ratio are acceptable as these are less than 0.90 (Hair et al., 2019). In Fornell and Larcker Criterion, constructs are sufficiently different and acceptable if all the diagonals values are greater than across the rows and columns as reported in Table 4. These two tables confirmed the individuality of each construct in the model. All these findings suggest that measurement model is valid and trustworthy and can be processed further.

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Table 3: Discriminant Validity through HTMT Ratio

HTMT	CWB	NL	OCB	OCC	OCE
CWB	1				
NL	0.434	1			
OCB	0.683	0.627	1		
OCC	0.338	0.755	0.729	1	
OCE	0.305	0.689	0.707	0.876	1

Table 4: Fornell and Larcker Criterion for Discriminant Validity

	CWB	NL	OCB	OCC	OCE
CWB	0.865				
NL	0.408	0.817			
OCB	0.597	0.552	0.854		
OCC	0.309	0.691	0.619	0.8	

Hypotheses Testing

After ensuring validity and reliability of the constructs, we ran the bootstrapping by using 5000 resamples to check the statistical significance and for estimation of standard error (SE). These SE are used to test significance of β coefficients through the t' values. The R Square for CWB was 0.269, OCC was 0.447, OCE was 0.375, and OCB was 0.247. By referring to the table 5 explain the hypothesized relationships here.

Figure 2 and Table 5 are the presentation of direct hypotheses of study. According to the H1, it was claimed that there is a positive relationship between NL and CWB and the same has been confirmed by the obtained results with $\beta=0.248$, ($t=5.133$, $p\text{-value}=0.005$). It means that NL has a positive and statistically significant relationship with CWB and reflected that narcissistic leaders can be a significant source of CWB in organizational settings. In the H2 it was proposed that the NL is positively related to OC and wherein OC was further measured by its three dimensions namely Cognitive (OCC), Emotional (OCE), and Behavioral (OCB) and in the form of hypotheses- H2(a), H2(b), and H2(c) respectively. H2(a) proposed that NL is positively related to OCC which has been found confirmed through the results which are showing $\beta=0.691$, ($t=11.788$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). H2(b) proposed that NL is also positively related to OCE as $\beta=0.634$, ($t=10.026$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). H2(c) stated that NL is positively related to OCB and found to be significant and confirmed as $\beta=0.552$, ($t=6.945$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Lastly, H3 was also segregated into three sub-hypotheses due to dimensions of OC as described earlier in section 2.

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H3(a) and H3(b) yielded insignificant findings and showed that OCC and OCE have negative influence on CWBs. H3(c) proposed that OCB is positively related to CWBs which has been found endorsed through the results $\beta=0.639$, ($t=6.688$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$).

Mediation Analysis

In the H4, it was proposed that OC mediates the relation between NL and CWBs and here all three dimensions of OC have been tested and presented in the last three rows of Table 5. Interestingly, it was observed that OCB is the only dimension of OC that significantly mediated the relation between NL and CWBs ($\beta=0.353$, $t=4.504$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$). Effect Size (f^2) also show that OCB had a moderate effect of 0.233. It can be seen that through the obtained results of this study that OCC and OCE, do not mediate the relationship between NL and CWBs as their indirect effects are insignificant at 5% level of significance.

Table 5: *Direct and Indirect Hypothesis Testing*

Hypothesis	Paths	B	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values	F Square
H1	NL -> CWB	0.248	0.080	5.133	0.005	0.040
H2 (a)	NL -> OCC	0.691	0.059	11.788	0.000	0.807
H2 (b)	NL -> OCE	0.634	0.063	10.026	0.000	0.599
H2 (c)	NL -> OCB	0.552	0.080	6.945	0.000	0.328
H3 (a)	OCC -> CWB	-0.147	0.152	0.968	0.333	0.013
H3 (b)	OCE -> CWB	-0.144	0.137	1.049	0.294	0.009
H3 (c)	OCB -> CWB	0.639	0.096	6.688	0.000	0.235
H4 (a)	NL -> OCC -> CWB	-0.102	0.107	0.947	0.344	0.014
H4 (b)	NL -> OCE -> CWB	-0.091	0.090	1.013	0.311	0.008
H4 (c)	NL -> OCB -> CWB	0.353	0.078	4.504	0.000	0.233

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Figure 2: Path Diagram of Structural Model

DISCUSSIONS

This study tries to investigate and highlight the mediating role of OC through its three dimensions i.e. OCC, OCE, & OCB in the relation between NL and CWBs in the public sector banks in Pakistan. Leadership is always an important construct and agent of change in this dynamic world, however, NL has proven itself a risk factor to resist the change and failure of organizations. There has been a huge reflection of several studies on multiple aspects but the researchers were unable to find any study which directly covered the mediation role of three dimensions of OC in the relation between NL and CWBs. This study contributes both theoretically and empirically to existing body of the literature.

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The findings of the study deduced that the NL has a significant impact on CWBs which is also supported by previous researchers (Braun et al., 2018; Grijalva & Newman, 2015). On the relationship between NL and CWBs, the results supported theoretical opinions embedded in social exchange theory (Blau, 1964) in which the employees look for reciprocity. The feeling of self-inclination by the NL and taking credit for all the success generates a counter-mechanism of CWBs to impact overall team efforts by the employees. The results also supported the theoretical arguments rooted in leader-member exchange theory (Deluga, 1998), which states that employees react to the narcissism of their leader with negative behaviors like cynicism and CWBs.

The findings of the study suggested that there is a direct relationship between NL & three dimensions of OC i.e. OCC, OCE, and OCB which is also supported by the arguments supporting SET (Blau, 1964) that the exchange taking place between employees and their leaders is mainly focused on fairness and honesty and on the basis of reciprocity. NL with the traits of patronizing the employees with egoistic and deceptive motives, raise the perception of dishonesty, unfairness and lack of integrity on part of organization and its leadership (Johnson et al., 2019). This feeling of negativity turns into emotional responses like anger, distrust, disgust, frustration and disappointments (Kiefer, 2005) which becomes OCB and sometimes this negative attitude directly turns into expressed OCB through actions and behaviors like making sarcastic comments in meetings, withdrawing or withholding efforts from teamwork, and making jokes about the leadership and the organization (Reichers et al., 1997). This ultimately impacts the nature of leader-member relation and also the overall performance of the organization as a whole.

The findings of the study suggest that out of three dimensions of OC only the OCB has a significant relationship with CWBs which means that only the employees with OCB tend to indulge in CWBs. This can be interpreted by the study lens of (Dean Jr et al., 1998) wherein it was stated that the OCC is more like a belief of lack of integrity and fairness whereas OCE is more like feeling the emotion but OCB is the cynical attitude with great likelihood of indulging in certain type of negative behaviors. There has been conflicting views whether the OC mediates the relationship between NL and CWBs (M. A. O. Ahmed et al., 2024), this study posits that OCB mediates significantly the relationship between NL and CWBs. The findings of the study infer the significant role of NL in emergence of employee negative attitudes and behaviors like OC and CWBs. Interestingly the study supports the argument that OCC and OCE dimensions of OC are just the believe and emotion which doesn't seem to reach the level of CWBs although the study finds significant impact of NL on three dimensional OC i.e. OCC, OCE, and OCB which means that NL can cause all these dimensions of OC but OCB has a significant impact on CWBs. The mediating role of OC was also found to be significant only in the case of OCB which means that only OCB mediates the relationship between NL and CWBs as can be seen in Table 5 the values of F square=0.233 which means the mediating role OCB plays between NL and CWB is medium to large (Cohen, 2013).

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CONCLUSION

The analysis performed in this study has shown a strong impact of NL on employee tendency to involve in CWBs. Furthermore, the organizations need to focus on the leadership roles to be assigned to people who believe in collaborative and participative leadership. Both the leader-member exchange theory and social exchange theory are supported i.e. the members try to reciprocate the behaviors of leadership which provides another scenario that the productivity of members and ultimate success of organizations majorly depend on the leadership characteristics. This study concludes that OCC, OCE, and OCB are significantly related to NL but only OCB is the mediator between the relationship of NL and CWBs. These findings reinforce the notion that even if one dimension of cynicism is driving negative behaviors, NL remains a destructive element that undermines employee well-being and organizational health. The leadership of an organization is the backbone for the emotional well-being of its employees and without supportive leadership, it is next to impossible for organizations to perform best in this dynamic environment – the organizational leadership can be a mean for organizational competitive advantage.

Theoretical Implications

Although there is a huge literature available on Leadership (Madi Odeh et al., 2023) but NL has been relatively unexplored (Aboramadan et al., 2021) especially in the banking industry. This study makes a substantial contribution by filling up the gap in the existing body of knowledge by checking the mediation role of OC between the relationship of NL and CWBs in the public banks of Pakistan.

Practical Implications

This study has not only contributed to theoretical knowledge but also to the practical terms by highlighting the significance of having right Leadership. In today's dynamic and rapidly changing work settings, it is crucial to keep the workforce aligned with organizational goals and Leadership has a very important role to keep workforce aligned in this ever changing environment. This study creates a significant need for leadership to avoid narcissistic traits at workplace as it not only creates negative attitude and behaviors in employees which impacts the team spirit of the employees but ultimately it causes a decrease in organizational performance. NL can promote OC and turn motivated and satisfied workforce into confused, disgusted and trouble making workforce which indulges into CWBs. This study offers huge implications for public sector banks working in the whole Pakistan to consider the impact of NL on the OCB and resultantly CWBs.

Social Implications

This study emphasizes that NL is not only an organizational concern but also a social issue which can trigger cynicism and counterproductive social behaviors that can extend to broader social relations. The study provides insights for public policy makers to launch policies based on trust, fairness and social support for the betterment of better societies.

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Limitations and Future Directions

This study is limited to Public Sector Banks operating in Pakistan. The use of convenience sampling can also be described as a limitation in generalizability of this study. Longitudinal and multinational studies can be done on the next step to understand the mediation role of all three dimensions of organizational cynicism. Furthermore, inclusion of other mediating variables can also be an interesting future endeavor.

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